

TIBIA

FEMUR

HUMERUS

CONTROL

RXR

Suppl. Fig. 1: Disrupted Growth Plate Morphology in P16 Female Rat Long Bones. Safranin O / fast green staining of bone sections highlights appearance of disturbed growth plate organization and fusion of primary and secondary ossification centers in the RXR agonist-treated females (scale bar = 200μm).